

**BASICS OF TEACHING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON
INFORMATION AND PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES**

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Abstract: *This article deals with the theoretical and practical foundations of teaching primary school students on the basis of information and pedagogical technologies, the concept and types of pedagogical technology for the implementation of innovative technologies.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, student, information, technology, innovation, teacher.*

In recent years, in the press, scientific literature, numerous conferences and meetings, as well as official documents "New pedagogical technologies", "Advanced pedagogical technologies", "Educational technologies", "Educational technologies", "Traditional pedagogical technologies", "Non-traditional pedagogical technologies", "Innovative (such concepts as new directions, new, newly introduced, new-like, non-traditional) pedagogical technologies". Since the concept of pedagogical technology is often used in pedagogical literature, opinions, attitudes and definitions to it are also different. Here are a few examples: "Pedagogical technology is the application of the ideas of systematization of education or systematization of teaching in the classroom to pedagogy (T. Sokomoto); "A systematized set of all means, tools and methods used to achieve pedagogical goals, and the procedure for their action" (M. V. Klarin); "Educational technology is the systematic application of scientific and other knowledge in solving practical problems" (T. Galbright); "Pedagogical technology is a process that guarantees the formation of personal qualities previously given to them as a product of the influence of a teacher (educator) on students (students) under certain conditions and using teaching (education) means" (N. Saidakhmedov); "Pedagogical technology is the design of the process of forming a student team, capable of guaranteeing pedagogical success, regardless of the

skill of the teacher” (V. P. Bepalko). According to V. Fefelov: "Pedagogical technology is a complex, interconnected and interacting block system that forms, develops and prepares a student based on the graduate model at a certain stage of education." In summary, UNESCO defines: "Pedagogical technology is a systematic approach to the creation, use and definition of the process of teaching and learning, taking into account technical and human capabilities and their interrelations, which aims to optimize the forms of learning. "From the above definitions, it can be seen that a systematic approach to education, unlike other approaches, determines the features of pedagogical technology. Thematic, defining learning objectives, designing the educational process, ensuring pedagogical success, interdependence and interacting blocks are important features and characteristics of pedagogical technology. In at the same time, it is necessary to include the reproducibility of technology in this series of symbols. It is known that the expected results are guaranteed in production, especially in technology used in industry. Also, the process of assembling parts created on the basis of thematic working drawings can be performed sequentially, repeatedly, that is, technological the cycle can be repeated, for example, imagine the process of creating cars produced at the joint venture "UzDaewooAvto" in Asaka. The same technological process, unique for each department of the enterprise, is repeated over and over again. the sample can be produced cars of the same appearance and quality. This feature of the technology is directly related to the pedagogical technological process. In the pedagogical process, it is more difficult to create a repeating, repeating cycle. This is due to the fact that the purpose of training, the content of the educational task, the variety of educational material, cognitive activity, the degree of mastering the individual characteristics of the student in many respects create certain difficulties.

However, to achieve success in the educational process, it is necessary to create a feedback of pedagogical technology, taking into account these difficulties. This fact was studied by Uzbek scientists U.N. Nishonaliev and B.L. Farberman gives the following definition of pedagogical technology: "Pedagogical technology is characterized by a clear setting of learning objectives, a guarantee of the final result, ensuring the repeatability of the learning process and the presence of rapid feedback." - defining learning goals, adjusting the process and learning goals, its guaranteed results, the presence of consistent feedback. Thus, the concept of pedagogical technology, in particular, new, innovative pedagogical technology The educational system consists of several interrelated components:

1. Shahe (swimmer);
2. Learning objectives;
3. Content of training;
4. Didactic (educational) process;
5. Forms of organization;
6. Pedagogical methods or technologies;

7. Teacher (tutor). As in the case with any theory, this system consists of two legitimate directions: x and a1: didactic (educational) tasks and ways to implement these tasks. Conventionally, if didactic (educational) questions include goals, forms, means, methods, they can be attributed to methods of implementation. Within the framework of this system, pedagogical methods or pedagogical technologies can be distinguished. Pedagogical technologies are an innovative approach to the educational process. This is an expression of social engineering thinking in pedagogy, a certain standardization of the process of education and upbringing. In particular, the rejection of preaching, oral teaching methods, computer-assisted teaching, technical teaching aids, a leader, an organizer, a student's cognitive activity consultant, a guide to the final result - a teacher, organizing students' independent work under the guidance of teachers lies in the fact that the leader has the ability to achieve almost the same end result. In particular, the current situation is especially important in the current period of training of specialists capable of meeting the requirements of the standards of the leading countries of the world, where uniform educational standards have been introduced. As a result of the organization of the learning process based on pedagogical technologies, educational goals are determined or predicted, the expected end result is a positive qualitative change, a repetitive cycle of the learning process is created, a quick reverse occurs or learning goals are adjusted. It should be noted that, according to the Uzbek scientist N. Saidakhmedov, "teachers often do not distinguish between methodology and technology. The methodology consists of a set of recommendations for organizing and conducting the educational process. The purpose of the methodology is to translate the theories of the subject into a concrete, plane of events ... Pedagogical technology is a mutual combat of the educational process; Organizational organization, construction, implementation, definition of components, achievement of goals, taking into account the available opportunities. Or PC is a set of procedures that resume the student's professional activity and guarantee the final result in education. Technology differs from methodology in its flexibility, variety of results, efficiency, the need for preliminary design" (Saidakhmedov N. New pedagogical technologies, V. 2003, p. 7). Pedagogical technologies used in practice can be divided into 12 types (G.K. Selevko, Modern educational technologies, M. 1998):

1. By the level of application (general pedagogical; special subject; local, modular, narrow pedagogical).

2. On a philosophical basis (materialism, idealism, dialectical, metaphysical, humanistic, anti-humanistic, anthroposophy, theosophy, pragmatism, existentialism, Zionism).

3. About the leading factors of mental development (biogenic, sociogenic, psychogenic, idealistic).

4. About the concept of assimilation (associative-reflexive, developing, behavioral, gestalt technology, suggestive, neurolinguistic).

5. About the personality structure (informational, operational, emotional, self-developing, heuristic and practical).

6. According to the content and nature of the structure (educational-pedagogical, secular-religious, general educational and professional, humanitarian-technocratic, diversified technologies, special-subject and monotechologies and polytechnologies).

7. By organizational forms (classroom, alternative, academic, individual, group, group learning, stratified learning).

8. By the type of organization and management of cognitive activity (classical lectures; reading with the help of audiovisual techniques; "consulting system"; learning with the help of books; "tutor" system; "program training" by V.P. Bespalko).

9. About the approach to the child (authoritarian, didactic-centric, personality-oriented technologies, collaborative technologies, free education technologies, esoteric technologies).

10. Priority methods (reproductive, explanatory, developing, problematic, creative, programmatic, interactive, gaming, self-learning, informational).

11. On the modernization of existing traditional systems (based on the humanization and democratization of relations; on the basis of the activation and acceleration of children's activities; on the basis of organizational and managerial efficiency; on the basis of methodological and didactic reconstruction of educational work). materials;

12. Taxation by categories of tuberculosis recipients (mass technology, advanced training, filler; technology of working with inappropriate, technology of working with twins). X, in the most developed countries of the world, such as AKD1, Great Britain, Japan, Germany, Turkey and Korea, as a result of such a new systematic approach to education, student learning is at a high level. In particular, 75% of the 50,000 swimmers trained as pedagogical technology experimenters in South Korea received positive feedback. In general, only the best swimmers can achieve such an indicator. The use of effective innovative pedagogical technologies in educational institutions of the republic leads to further improvement of educational processes, bringing the quality of education up to world standards, training personnel in accordance with the requirements of the Unified State Educational Standards. In the future, pedagogical technology will become richer both theoretically and practically. The Uzbek people will create a solid technical foundation in accordance with the national characteristics of pedagogy, the ideas of the ideology of national development.

The emergence and development of a technological approach to the educational process, including teaching, has a long history. From the history of our schools, from the research of our scientists, it is known that the development of this approach to the educational process can be divided into three stages. At the first stage, the learning process is carried out only by the teacher, the experience and knowledge accumulated by mankind are transferred to the student only through the teacher. At the second stage, textbooks and manuals began to be published. Didactic materials appeared to

help the teacher. At the third stage, the content of learning technology became richer than before: technical means for teachers and students, learning machines were added, and the concept of programmed learning appeared. New approaches have begun to emerge to help maintain the effectiveness of education. A technological approach to the problem of raising the efficiency of education to a high level appeared in the 1930s. During this period, the concept of "pedagogical technique⁴¹" appeared in the specialized literature, defined as learning; and as a set of methods and tools for effective organization. In the 1940s and early 1950s, the period of introducing technical teaching aids into the educational process began.

In particular, cinema, radio, controls, and ways of using them are equated to pedagogical technologies. In the mid-1950s, a movement arose in world pedagogy to organize the learning process in a unique "technological" way. However, in the 1960s, the variety of teaching methods made it difficult to use them effectively, and it became necessary to create a common scientific basis for these methods. As a result, the technology of pedagogical methods, the theoretical and practical foundations of teaching technology began to take shape. In 1961, the Pedagogical Technology magazine began to be published in AKD1. In 1964 the journal "Pedagogical Technology and Program Education" 44 was published in England, in 1965 in Japan, in 1971 in Italy "Pedagogical Technology" 44 .

LINKS AND RECOMMENDED READING:

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